

EMPOWERING BEHAVIORS OF SCHOOL HEADS AS PREDICTOR OF TEACHER TEACHING EFFICACY AND JOB SATISFACTION

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Abstract. This study evaluated the role of the empowering behaviors of the school heads to the job satisfaction and teaching efficiency of teachers. This study also utilized non-experimental quantitative research using the descriptive method by which the main tool was adapted and modified from the standardized survey questionnaire. In selecting the respondents, the researcher identified at least 150 total population of teachers and used pure random sampling. The elementary teachers of Maco North District, Division of Davao de Oro, particularly teacher I to master teacher II teachers with at least three to five years in the teaching service and above have undergone supervision from the school heads. The empowering behavior of the school heads in terms of acknowledgment and recognition, fostering collaborative relationships, and providing role-modeling was oftentimes manifested. The extent of teaching proficiency of teachers in terms of social presence, cognitive presence and teaching presence was oftentimes manifested. The job satisfaction of teachers in terms of teacher cooperation, teacher workload, and leadership support was oftentimes manifested. The teaching efficacy of teachers was oftentimes manifested in terms of efficacy in student engagement, efficacy in Instructional Strategies, efficacy in classroom management. Hence, these are all a manifestation of significant relationship between empowering behaviors of the school heads to the job satisfaction of teachers, and the teaching proficiency of teachers.

KEY WORDS

1. Empowering behaviors of School Heads
2. Teacher Job Satisfaction
3. Teaching Efficacy

1. Introduction

As the main person in the school organization, the school head was very important in empowering their followers, subordinates, and employees to own and demonstrate any or all of the leadership behaviors they have learned about. The empowered teachers feel more confident in their abilities and tend to deliver projects with greater care. By implementing an empowering leadership strategy, leaders allow employees to take ownership of their work, resulting in increased productivity, happier employees, and a healthy workplace culture. In the global context, Winn, Cothorn, Lastrapes, and Orange (2021). leadership is the most crucial component of education. Effective leaders are the key to meaningful teacher support and development, which leads to high-quality teachers (Leithwood et al., 2004). They also suggested ineffective leader-

ship may cause the best teachers to falter, leave a school, or worse, exit the profession. In a comprehensive meta-analysis, Waters et al. (2003) asserted that effective principal leadership encompasses the what, when, how, and why of doing things, along with a leader who imparts the vision to others in a way that influences them to follow. Support from administrators and supervisors is defined as providing for staff members' needs to boost performance levels, engaging in supportive activities that help staff members feel like valuable assets and improve their quality of life at work, and fostering a positive working environment (Bhanthumnavin, 2003). Employee attitudes and expectations toward their work and the organization are called job satisfaction. Employees' general attitudes and thoughts toward their work and the organization can be inferred from their level of job satisfaction (Aziri, 2011). The person has wants, needs, and expectations for their professional lives. The degree to which teachers believe they can complete a task by taking the necessary steps is correlated with how effective they think their instruction is. A more effective teacher will foster a supportive learning environment, support students' feelings, and attend to their needs (Khanshan, and Yousefi, 2020). Principals must support teachers in creating a school climate where teachers are valued, where they can work peacefully and comfortably, where their ideas, requests, and complaints are considered, where their problems are solved effectively, and where their achievements are appreciated. Therefore, it can be assumed that the support from the principal is effective in ensuring teachers' job satisfaction and teaching efficiency (Wang, 2014). One of the challenges in China is that kindergarten teachers are vastly overworked (Li et al., 2019). According to a recent government report, kindergarten education would require at least 520,000 teachers by the end of 2018. (Chen, 2019). Improving kindergarten teachers' job satisfaction may be an excellent way to reduce the teacher shortage

temporarily. While in Asia-Pacific countries, teachers from China, 34.6 In the Philippines, particularly in the study of Aquino et. al. (2021) at the Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines, it was found out that the school head is the axis around which many elements of the school take precedence. He is responsible for every dimension of the operation of the system, be it academic or administrative. The school head must be inclined to make almost all of the school's decisions. Thus, the school head must be a director, a planner, and a judgment-maker. A trustworthy school head would use collaboration as a working technique by establishing teams and smaller units of team members to examine proposals or tactics. Therefore, it is up to the school head to be a strong team player to impact the quality of instruction. While in it was also stated that in public primary schools of Calabar, Division of Misamis Occidental, a study revealed that head teachers' decision-making strategy and leadership style have a significant influence on teachers' task performance in the sampled schools. Also, head teachers' communication skills significantly relate to teachers' task performance in the area. Proper managerial behavior to boost teachers' morale toward high task performance has to be adopted (Baluyos et al. 2019). In the Davao Region, it was found that there is a crisis in teaching efficacy, which significantly predicts the job satisfaction and teaching efficacy of teachers, especially in the provinces of Davao del Sur, Davao Oriental, Davao del Norte, Davao de Oro, and Davao Occidental with six cities, namely: Davao City, Digos City, Tagum City, Panabo City, Mati City, and the Island Garden City of Samal, with 1,340 public teachers. The high mean ratings of its indicators, action, preventive, achievement, and uncertainty management, ranging from 3.76 to 3.94 as evaluated by the teacher respondents, were found to be the cause of the high level of crisis self-efficacy among public school teachers among public schools in Region XI, the Philippines. High

level indicates that teachers in public schools frequently demonstrate their crisis-teaching effectiveness. Meanwhile, in Furthermore, data suggests that educators take the necessary steps to safeguard students at the workplace. The findings demonstrated that teachers' commitment to their jobs is significantly predicted by how well they manage uncertainty in the classroom (Baloran, and Hernan, 2020). The researcher finds it urgent to study the role of the school heads, particularly the principal, as they possess the potential and responsibility to influence teacher job satisfaction and teaching efficiency. They were

uniquely positioned and have an unparalleled opportunity to create and foster the conditions in which many variables come together and significantly impact teachers. The school heads' empowering behaviors influence teachers' satisfaction and efficacy in teaching. Satisfied teachers were able to accept more job demands and faceless emotional exhaustion. Furthermore, existing research shows that teachers who were happy with their work can generate more positive effects for their students. Finally, when job satisfaction and teaching efficiency are high, teachers are less likely to quit.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework— This quantitative research is based on the Management Theory X and Y which proposed by McGregor's (1950) as cited by Lapuz and Pecajas (2022). Management Theory X conveys the importance of heightened supervision, external rewards, and penalties, while Theory Y highlights the motivating role of job satisfaction, which encourages workers to approach tasks without direct supervision. The proponent further posited that the management use of Theory X and Y can affect employee motivation and productivity in different ways, and managers may choose to implement strategies from both theories into their practices. Thus, school heads, as managers of the school within their jurisdiction, are important individuals in achieving their goals. It must be noted that the management style of the school heads impacts the teachers' performance, and the school in general. Hence, with the guidance and supervision of the school heads, teachers and other school personnel can work efficiently and productively, according to the standards of the Department of Education. Hutton (2013) also added that his could mean that the teachers and other school personnel become effective and efficient in their job if school heads as leaders appropriately practice their authority, accountability, and empowerment. As further stated in the Theories of Management (X

and Y), it is likely that a manager will need to adopt both approaches depending on the evolving circumstances and levels of internal and external locus of control throughout the workplace. The theories cited were applicable and insightful about the present study. These Management Theories can be used by school heads to formulate and develop motivation and positive management styles, strategies, and techniques. Added to, the three theories of empowerment, instructional leadership, and distributed leadership serve as the foundation for the study. The School Management Team (SMT) can perform instructional leadership thanks to empowerment, and distributed leadership serves as the mechanism through which empowerment can occur. This is how the three theories are intertwined. In essence, the principal must carry out the responsibilities of instructional leadership in order to enable the SMT to do the same. Someone who is unable to perform a task cannot expect others to do it for them. The practice of distributed leadership is one method by which empowerment may occur. Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework and serves as the schemata of the study. In this study, two variables are being illustrated. The first variable, which serves as the exogenous variable, is the empowering behaviors of the school heads that contains an indicator which is giving acknowledgment and recog-

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework of the study

Empowering behaviors of school heads, such as providing recognition, fostering collaborative relationships, and providing role-modelling while there is two endogenous variable in this study, namely the Job Satisfaction with three corresponding indicators namely teacher cooperation, teacher workload, leadership support and the Teaching Efficiency with three corresponding indicators namely efficacy in student engagement, efficacy in instructional strategies and efficacy in classroom

1.2. Statement of the Problem—This study aimed to evaluate the role of the empowering behaviors of the school heads in job satisfaction and teaching efficiency. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What is the extent of technology literacy of the empowering behavior of the school heads in terms of:
 - (1) Giving acknowledgement and Recognition
 - (2) Fostering Collaborative Relationships
 - (3) Providing role-modelling
- (2) What is the extent of job satisfaction of teachers in terms of:
 - (1) Teacher cooperation
 - (2) Teacher workload
 - (3) Leadership support
- (3) What is the extent of Teaching efficacy of teachers in terms of:
 - (1) Efficacy in Student Engagement
 - (2) Efficacy in Instructional Strategies
 - (3) Efficacy in Classroom Management
- (4) Is there any significant relationship between
 - (1) Empowering behavior of the school heads to the Job Satisfaction of teachers

- (2) Empowering behavior of the school heads to the teaching proficiency of teachers
- (5) Which of the domains of the empowering behavior of the school heads significantly influence the Job Satisfaction and teaching proficiency teachers?

1.3. Hypothesis—The hypothesis were tested at $\alpha=0.05$ level of significance. H01: There is no significant relationship between empowering behavior of the school heads on the Job Satisfaction and teaching proficiency teachers. H02: None of the domains of the empowering behavior of the school heads significantly influence the Job Satisfaction and teaching proficiency teachers. The findings of the study may benefit the following: School heads and Administrators. The data and information collected on this study would serve as a platform for the school heads and administrators to create dynamic schemes in his or her supervision of school activities for the betterment of the school as well as of the teachers by means of helping them grow particularly on their empowering behavior of the school heads significantly influence the Job Satisfaction and teaching proficiency teachers. They could also become the motivational driving force to keep the teachers' burning passion for serving this generation's young minds. Teachers. This study would also be significant because the empowering behavior of the school heads significantly influences the Job Satisfaction and teaching proficiency of teachers. It also improves their teaching competencies and helps them proceed with the teaching and learning process effectively, as they serve as the wheel of education and the facilitator of learning. Lastly, this study would serve as a reference for future researchers as they conduct similar or comparative studies. To ensure an understanding of the terms used in the study, the following are defined conceptually and operationally: School Heads' empowering behaviors refer to encouraging self-reward systems, self-leadership, opportunity awareness, participation in goal setting, and independent behavior by followers and group members. In other words, it's all about helping followers take ownership of their positions toward the organization's greater good (Lynch, 2015). In this study, empowering behaviors of school heads are used to refer to the leadership that the school heads possess in terms of managing the teachers in actualizing the goals of the school by means of upholding empowering behaviors of school heads. Job Satisfaction of Teachers refers to the overall commitment and productivity of the school organization. It was any combination of psychological, physiological, and environmental circumstances that cause a person to truthfully say that they are satisfied with a job (Bourne, 2022). In this study, this refers to how satisfied the teachers in the teaching field as influenced by the empowering behaviors of school heads. Teaching Efficiency of Teachers was defined as the efficacy as the ability of a teacher to produce effective learning outcomes is referred to as teacher efficacy (Isiksal, 2010). This refers to how efficient the teachers are in the instructional process as influenced by the empowering behaviors of school heads.

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research design, the research participants, the research instrument, data gathering, and the data analysis to be used in the study. In this study, to determine the significant relationship between the school heads' empowering behaviors and teachers' job satisfaction and teaching efficiency, the researcher utilized non-experimental quantitative research using a descriptive method, in which the main tool was adapted and modified from the standardized survey questionnaire. According to Anastasi (2005), this specific type of research design is

appropriate when a researcher would like to trace the significance of the relationship between variables. Since this study contains two variables and this research study aimed to measure the degree of relationship between the independent variable, which was technology literacy, and the dependent variable, which was the teaching process of teachers, this kind of research method was used. Quantitative research could be divided into two general categories experimental and non-experimental. The experimental study was to provide strong evidence for cause-and-effect relationships. This is done by demonstrating that manipulations of at least one variable, called the treatment or independent variable, produce different outcomes in another variable, called the dependent variable. On the other hand, non-experimental quantitative research is empirical, using numeric and quantifiable data. Conclusions were based on experimentation and objective and systematic observations. Non-experimental research involves variables that were not manipulated by the researcher and were studied as they exist. One reason for using non-experimental research is that many variables of interest in social science cannot be manipulated because they are attribute variables, such as gender, socioeconomic status, learning style, or any other personal characteristic or trait (Belli, G., 2008). Descriptive research was defined by Bhat (2019) as a research method that describes the characteristics of the population or phenomenon that was being studied. This methodology focuses more on the “what” of the research subject rather than the “why” of the research subject. Moreover, according to Hale (2018), there were three main types of descriptive methods: observational, case study, and survey. The observational Method is sometimes also called field observation, where animal and human behavior is closely observed. The Case study research involves an in-depth study of an individual. This type of study often leads to testable hypotheses and allows us to study rare phenomena. Case studies should not be used to determine cause and effect, and they are limited to making accurate predictions—lastly, the Survey Method. In survey method research, participants answer questions administered through interviews or questionnaires. After participants answer the questions, researchers describe the responses given. For the survey to be both reliable and valid, it is essential that the questions are constructed properly. Questions should be written so they are straightforward and easy to comprehend.

2.1. Research Respondents—The respondents of this study were the elementary teachers of the nearby schools of Maco North District, Division of Davao de Oro. In selecting the respondents, the researcher identified at least 150 total population of teachers and used pure random sampling. The said respondents are teacher I to master teacher II teachers of Maco North District in the Division of Davao de Oro with at least three to five years in the teaching service and above who have undergone supervision from the school heads.

2.2. Research Instrument—The researcher used two sets of instruments in this study. To ensure that the appropriateness of the study was appropriately addressed, the questionnaire of

the independent variable, the empowering behaviors of school heads having the indicators giving acknowledgment and recognition, fostering collaborative relationships, and providing role-modeling was adapted and modified from the study of Lapuz and Pecajas (2022) to give the present study while the job satisfaction with three corresponding indicators namely teacher cooperation, teacher workload, leadership support as its indicators will be adapted from the study of Toropova Myrberg and Johansson (2021) and the teaching efficiency of teachers and the Teaching Efficiency with three corresponding indicators namely efficacy in student engagement, efficacy in instructional strategies and efficacy in classroom management adapted

from the study of Tschannen-Moran and Woolfolk Hoy (2001). The indicators of both the independent variables and the dependent variables were carefully chosen and were improved after several consultations and discussions with the adviser. The final copy was validated by the panel of experts for approval, and the final revision was made by incorporating the corrections, comments, and suggestions given by the experts before distribution and administration. The pilot testing conducted with the 30 respondents was not included in the research survey.

Moreover, a survey instrument was developed to determine the essence of the variable in developing the instructional process. The reliability was measured with a Cronbach alpha of 0.75, which means reliable, since according to Explorable.com (2010), the considered reliable range is between 0.70 and 1.00. The five-point Likert scale was utilized in this study to describe the presence of the provisions relating to the empowering behaviors of school heads as follows:

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very Extensive	Empowering behaviors of school heads is always manifested.
3.41-4.19	Extensive	Empowering behaviors of school heads is oftentimes manifested.
2.60-3.40	Moderately Extensive	Empowering behaviors of school heads is sometimes manifested.
1.80-2.59	Less Extensive	Empowering behaviors of school heads is seldom manifested.
1.00-1.79	Not Extensive	Empowering behaviors of school heads is never manifested.

On the other hand, provisions relating to the extent of Job satisfaction are as follows:

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very Extensive	Job satisfaction of teachers is always manifested.
3.41-4.19	Extensive	Job satisfaction of teachers is oftentimes manifested.
2.60-3.40	Moderately Extensive	Job satisfaction of teachers is sometimes manifested.
1.80-2.59	Less Extensive	Job satisfaction of teachers is seldom manifested.
1.00-1.79	Not Extensive	Job satisfaction of teachers is never manifested.

Moreover, provisions relating to the extent of teaching efficacy are as follows:

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Descriptive Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very Extensive	Teaching efficacy of teachers is always manifested.
3.41-4.19	Extensive	Teaching efficacy of teachers is oftentimes manifested.
2.60-3.40	Moderate Extensive	Teaching efficacy of teachers is sometimes manifested.
1.80-2.59	Less Extensive	Teaching efficacy of teachers is seldom manifested.
1.00-1.79	Not Extensive	Teaching efficacy of teachers is never manifested.

2.3. *Data Gathering Procedure*—The following procedures were necessary for the data gathering: The researcher secured an endorsement letter from the dean of graduate school to the school division Superintendent to survey the elementary and secondary teachers. Letters of permission were sent to the district supervisor and all principals of the selected schools in the said schools. The arrangement was made with the district supervisor and school principals regarding the conduct of the research. After the approval, the researcher personally distributed and administered the survey questionnaires on the teachers’ technology literacy and teaching proficiency. The researcher secured a Certificate of Appearance from the principals to verify that the researcher conducted and collected the data from the study participants. The data gathered were tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted confidentially and accordingly with the assistance of the research adviser and statistician. The study took approximately nine months to complete, from the conceptualization of the title and outline to the data collection, analysis of findings, summary, conclusion, and

recommendation. That was, in this study, from June 2022 to March 2023. The researcher observed full ethical standards in the study, following the study protocol assessment and standardized criteria, particularly in managing the population and the data. The elementary and secondary teachers from different schools were given free will to participate or withdraw without any consequence or penalty. Therefore, after the purpose and benefit of the study were described and presented to the teachers, the right of the respondents to contribute to the body of knowledge was carefully considered and adhered to.

2.4. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tool was used in this study: Mean was used to measure the empowering behaviors of the school heads to the job satisfaction and teaching efficiency of teachers Pearson r was used to determine the significant relationship between the empowering behaviors of the school heads and the job satisfaction and teaching efficiency of teachers. Regression Analysis was used to determine the relationships between teacher job satisfaction and teaching efficiency and the school heads’ empowering behaviors.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the discussions of the problems in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed, and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: empowering behaviors of school heads as a predictor to teaching efficacy and job satisfaction

3.1. *Empowering Behaviors of School Leaders in terms of Giving Acknowledgement and Recognition*—Shown in Table 1 are data on empowering behaviors of school leaders in terms of giving acknowledgement and recognition. The presentation is focused on the highest, middle, and lowest mean ratings; the findings obtained primarily denote that the school leader always gives me positive feedback when I perform well the highest (4.06) and personally compliments me when I do outstanding work (4.04); Receiving sufficient institutional recognition for teaching performance, (4.01) and Gives me special recognition when my work is very good,(4.00); and Delegates authority to me that is equal to the level of responsi-

bility that I am assigned, (3.78) which is considered as the lowest among the items. This has gained (3.97) as the overall mean, which means that for all items in this indicator, the empowering behaviors of school leaders in terms of giving acknowledgment and recognition are oftentimes manifested as descriptive equivalents. Furthermore, the results gathered for the giving acknowledgment and recognition reveals that almost all respondents agreed that school leaders must possess qualities aside from providing fortified skills to the teachers; they should always be given acknowledgment and recognition, particularly for performing well in the instructional process. As they acknowledge and recognize the issue, school leaders will be the benchmark in incorporating teacher support.

Table 1. Empowering Behaviors of School Leaders in terms of Giving Acknowledgement and Recognition

No.	Statement	Mean (\bar{x})	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Personally compliments me when I do outstanding work	4.04	Extensive
2	Delegates authority to me that is equal to the level of responsibility that I am assigned.	3.78	Extensive
3	Gives me special recognition when my work is very good	4.00	Extensive
4	Receiving sufficient institutional recognition for teaching performance.	4.01	Extensive
5	Always gives me positive feedback when I perform well.	4.06	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.97	Extensive

Similarly, the finding is supported by the study of Andrews (2011) that Being recognized is a really fulfilling experience for a great classroom for the teachers. Teachers’ recognition is based on some well-known ideas of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. It gives the other educators striving to enhance student learning outcomes hope for genuine recognition. Students of the teacher, the administration, the governing board, and the general public all show pride and

support. Moreover, the teaching profession offers many benefits that motivate people to work in the field. When teachers are acknowledged. Teachers work countless hours to advance their practice and are passionate about what they do. It makes sense that receiving praise for one’s own efforts would improve performance. Extrinsic motivations are described as acting in a way that will result in a distinct outcome, which can also be used to encourage workers to put in

more effort. A teacher may be able to have a positive effect on students when they are recog-

nized. As a result, this might also improve the atmosphere at work (Movsessian, 2018).

3.2. *Fostering Collaborative Relationships*—Presented in Table 2 are data on the empowering behaviors of school leaders in terms of in terms of fostering collaborative relationships. The presentation concentrates on the indicators with the rating obtained from highest to the least of the following: I ask people who have had similar experiences what they did (4.05) as the highest rating; fosters collaboration among staff members (4.03); I try to get advice from someone about what to do (4.01); encourages staff members to be team players (3.99); and gets staff members to work together for the same goal (3.98) as least mean rating. The overall mean contains the descriptive equivalent of extensive and with 4.00 as its value, which connotes that the empowering behaviors of school

leaders in terms of fostering collaborative relationships are oftentimes manifested. On the other words, the data finding suggests that the teachers indeed suffice their teaching and engage on their learning process by means of the collaborative relationship as they were rated extensive in this indicator. Likewise, the result shows that the school leaders must provide heightened collaborative relationships among the administrators and teachers as well as teachers to teachers of since they incorporate their teaching pedagogy with one another. This has a connotation when teachers are satisfied and have a collaborative relationship with their co-teachers as well as on the administrators, they can proceed with their teaching procedures and can work efficiently inside the classroom.

Table 2. Empowering Behaviors of School Leaders in terms of Fostering Collaborative Relationships

No.	Statement	Mean (\bar{x})	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Fosters collaboration among staff members	4.03	Extensive
2	I try to get advice from someone about what to do	4.01	Extensive
3	Encourages staff members to be team players	3.99	Extensive
4	I ask people who have had similar experiences what they did	4.05	Extensive
5	Gets staff members to work together for the same goal	3.98	Extensive
Overall Mean		4.01	Extensive

This statement conforms the idea that teachers and principals at schools must collaborate and commit to a collaborative culture. Each of these collaborative activities, common planning

time, professional learning communities, and critical friend groups require regular, set aside time for teachers. With time, teachers can create genuine collaborative groups that address

shared problems, objectives, or school-wide initiatives, take part in cooperative projects using group resources, and develop their abilities,

knowledge, and character traits related to student learning (Caskey and Carpenters, (2014).

3.3. *Providing Role-modelling*—Table 3 reveals the data on the empowering behaviors of school leaders in terms of providing role-modeling. The statements in the indicators are presented logically from the highest to lowest mean rating obtained, namely: Sets a good example by the way they behave with the mean of (4.04) that serves as the highest; Works as hard as anyone in my school with a mean rating of (4.01); Leads by example which contains the mean rating of (3.99); Gives me the authority to make changes necessary to improve things having the mean of (3.98); and Delegates authority to me that is equal to the level of responsibility that I am assigned with the mean rating of 3.93

that shares as the lowest among the indicators for providing role-modeling. The overall mean of (3.99) with the descriptive equivalent of extensive means that the empowering behaviors of school leaders in terms of providing role-modelling is oftentimes manifested. Furthermore, the finding implies that as the teachers invigorate themselves in performing well inside and outside the classroom or as a role model when school leaders provide them good role-modelling. Providing role-modelling highlights one of the good characteristics of empowered school leaders, which will give the ladder for his subordinates to incorporate towards the teaching pedagogy.

Table 3. Empowering Behaviors of School Leaders in terms of Providing Role-Modelling

No.	Statement	Mean (\bar{x})	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Gives me the authority to make changes necessary to improve things	3.98	Extensive
2	Delegates authority to me that is equal to the level of responsibility that I am assigned	3.93	Extensive
3	Works as hard as anyone in my school	4.01	Extensive
4	Sets a good example by the way they behave	4.04	Extensive
5	Leads by example	3.99	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.99	Extensive

Thus, this result revealed that the study, according to Robbins (2003), leadership was the ability to persuade people to work toward a common goal. Role modeling was one of the most effective strategies for influencing the behavior of subordinates. Moreover, one of a leader’s assets and the secret to their success was their ability to set an example. A leader served as an

example for the other members of the organization. The ”model for desired and appropriate behaviors” should be a principal. His behavior was imitated and had an impact on how his subordinates behaved. Therefore, everyone could learn through observation, interaction, and interaction with others, including a leader, in addition to direct experiences (Balyer, 2017).

3.4. *Summary on the Empowering Behaviors of School Leaders*—Presented in Table 4 are the data on the summary of the empowering behaviors of school leaders. The overall mean of the data in this table is (4.00). The indicators are presented with corresponding means: Giving acknowledgment and Recognition with a mean of (3.97), Providing role-modelling, which gained a mean of (4.01), and Giving acknowledgment and Recognition (3.99). All of these

indicators are presented randomly with the descriptive equivalent of extensive. The extensive mean rating in this table suggests that a summary of empowering behaviors of school leaders is oftentimes manifested, which means that the teachers agreed that the empowering behaviors of school leaders are indeed a predictor of the effective companion of the improvement of the teaching skills in developing work success, particularly teaching efficiency and job satisfaction.

Table 4. Summary on the Empowering Behaviors of School Leaders

Indicators	Mean (\bar{x})	Descriptive Equivalent
Giving acknowledgement and Recognition	3.97	Extensive
Providing role-modelling	4.01	Extensive
Giving acknowledgement and Recognition	3.99	Extensive
Overall Mean	4.00	Extensive

3.5. *Teacher Job Satisfaction in terms of Teacher Cooperation*—Table 5 presents the data gathered regarding teacher job satisfaction in terms of teacher cooperation. The gathered data were arranged logically from the highest to the lowest mean rating, namely: Collaborate in planning and preparing instructional materials with a rating of (4.07); Share what I have

learned about my teaching experiences with (4.05) mean rating; Work together to try out new ideas having the rating of (4.01); Work with teachers from other grades to ensure continuity in learning with the rating of (3.99); and lastly, discuss how to teach a particular topic having the rating of (3.90) which contains the lowest mean rating among them all.

Moreover, the overall mean rating for teacher job satisfaction in terms of teacher cooperation was (3.99) with the descriptive equivalent of extensive and is primarily oftentimes manifested. Furthermore, the finding implies that teacher cooperation molds the teachers to be satisfied with the field of teaching as this emulsifies bond as well as support system with one another. This also connotes the embodiment of the cooperative status of the teachers

as they uphold dealing with collaborative perspectives and primarily to dwell unto the advance features that the new and the upcoming generations. Collectively, this is parallel to the study of Woods and Roberts (2019), where a growing body of research supports the idea that utilizing distributed leadership’s potential can improve learning and give schools more room to grow. That is, more people at all school levels become actively involved in enhancing learn-

Table 5. Teacher Job Satisfaction in terms of Teacher Cooperation

No.	Statement	Mean(\bar{x})	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Work with teachers from other grades to ensure continuity in learning	3.99	Extensive
2	Collaborate in planning and preparing instructional materials	4.07	Extensive
3	Share what I have learned about my teaching experiences	4.05	Extensive
4	Discuss how to teach a particular topic impressions of some course participants	3.90	Extensive
6	Work together to try out new ideas	4.01	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.99	Extensive

ing and their knowledge, capabilities, and skills. This includes teachers, students, and others. Opportunities for group learning are expanding. Encouragement rises. Both faculty and students now have a greater passion for and dedication to the school’s community and to education, both their own and others.

3.6. *Teacher Workload*—Table 6 shows the data on teacher job satisfaction in terms of teacher workload. The data was arranged from the highest to the lowest mean rating obtained: I have too many administrative tasks with a rating of (4.02) which serves as the highest; I need more time to prepare for class with a rating of (4.00); I need more time to assist individual students with the mean of (3.93); I need more time to prepare for class having the mean of (3.78);

The finding conforms to the statement of the OECD (2006), which asserts that intensification degrades the quality of teachers’ responsibility to deliver high-quality instruction. Teacher workloads have a direct impact on the effectiveness of teaching and learning. This occurs when a teacher is assigned too many tasks and responsibilities that she is unable to complete, which primarily results in a loss of time that the latter could have spent instructing her students.

and The teacher can utilize a variety of information sources to explore problems posed in this course with the mean of (3.77) that serves the lowest among them. All items in this indicator yield ratings with a descriptive equivalent of extensive. This has gained an overall mean rating of (3.95) extensive or a descriptive equivalent of extensive, meaning that job satisfaction in teacher workload is often manifested. This result reveals that teachers demonstrate the importance of workload as a manifestation of job satisfaction. Workload is one of the essential things that school leaders must uphold. Giving teachers a heavy workload greatly affects their performance as well as their professional growth. Thus, a school leader must give greater emphasis on giving teachers workloads equally.

Added to, since it helps students succeed, effective teaching is unquestionably important and necessary in education (Chirimi, 2016). The academic progress of students throughout their education reflects the quality of the teacher’s classroom instruction. Furthermore, according to modern educational theory, teachers should support learning so that students can fully or partially understand the complexities of people and the wider world. However, the distribution

Table 6. Job Satisfaction in terms of Teacher Workload

No.	Statement	Mean(\bar{x})	Descriptive Equivalent
1	I need more time to prepare for class	3.78	Extensive
2	I have too many administrative tasks	4.02	Extensive
4	I need more time to assist individual students	3.93	Extensive
5	The teacher is able to utilize a variety of information sources to explore problems posed in this course.	3.77	Extensive
6	I need more time to prepare for class	4.00	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.92	Extensive

of workloads makes it difficult for teachers to manage their time and other tasks.

3.7. *Leadership Support*—Table 7 shows the data collected on job satisfaction in terms of leadership support. The presentation of the data gathered is arranged logically from the highest to the lowest or in other words, in a logical manner obtained, namely: School leadership’s support for teachers’ professional development which garnered the mean rating of

(4.00); Amount of instructional support provided to teachers by school leadership with the mean of (3.90); Is always seeking new opportunities for the school with the rating of (3.89); Gives me the authority I need to make decisions that improve work processes and procedures which both gained the mean of (3.88) as the lowest. All five items on these indicators conceded extensive as their descriptive equivalents.

Table 7. Job Satisfaction in terms of Leadership Support

No.	Statement	Mean(\bar{x})	Descriptive Equivalent
1	School leadership’s support for teachers’ professional development	4.00	Extensive
2	Gives me the authority I need to make decisions that improve work processes and procedures teacher can help to keep the students	3.88	Extensive
3	Amount of instructional support provided to teachers by school leadership	3.90	Extensive
4	Is always seeking new opportunities for the school	3.89	Extensive
5	Collaboration between school leadership and teachers to plan instruction	3.88	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.95	Extensive

Likewise, this has gained an overall mean of (3.95) with a descriptive equivalent of extensive that primarily indicates that the teacher

respondents underpin that the job satisfaction of teachers also matters in terms of leadership support and is often manifested. Leadership sup-

port primarily conforms to how school leaders support and involve teachers in decision making, support for instructional materials as well as for professional development. This primarily involves the enhancement of the teaching skills in sustaining the innovations of the learning activities and addressing issues inside and outside the classroom by means of sufficient teaching practice in delivering the different kinds and modes of instruction. In summary, progressive school improvement initiatives across several states have assumed a key position. This has been achieved by making excellent classroom instruction the focal point of improvement initiatives and by giving teacher leaders the power, tools, and training to spearhead these initiatives in collaboration with school administrators. Academic achievement for students with high needs has significantly and sustainably improved because teacher leaders are given a leading role in designing and delivering professional learning (Combs and Silverman, 2016).

3.8. *Summary of Teacher Job Satisfaction*—Table 8 presents the summary of Teacher

Job Satisfaction, which contains three indicators arranged randomly and shows that the overall mean is (3.95) having the descriptive equivalent of high. The three indicators are presented with their corresponding mean rating, namely: Leadership support (3.99), Teacher cooperation (3.92), and Teacher workload (3.95). The results suggest that most of the participants were satisfied with their current position and performed in their individual school functions effectively, as they rated this variable as extensive. This statement conforms to the idea of Jupp (2009), who stressed that teacher efficiency is best defined as the practical outputs of teaching. These outputs are quantitative student learning, as calculated by value-added assessments, particularly which measure how much a specific teacher improves an individual student’s education or other rigorous measures. They are qualitative observations of a teacher’s classroom performance by a principal or peer who understands the classroom practices that improve student achievement.

Table 8. Summary on teaching proficiency of teachers

Indicators	Mean(\bar{x})	Descriptive Equivalent
Leadership support	3.99	Extensive
Teacher cooperation	3.92	Extensive
Teacher workload	3.95	Extensive
Overall mean	3.95	Extensive

3.9. *Teacher Teaching Efficacy in terms of Efficacy in Student Engagement*—Table 9 presents the data gathered regarding the efficacy of teacher teaching in terms of student engagement. The collected data were arranged logically from the highest to the lowest mean rating, namely: You can assist families in helping their children do well in school and can help your students think critically both with the rating of (4.05); You can foster student creativity having

the rating of (4.01); You can get through to the most difficult students with the rating of (3.94); and lastly, You can foster students creativity having the rating of (3.90) which contains the lowest mean rating among them all. Moreover, the overall mean rating for the teacher teaching efficacy in terms of efficacy in student engagement was (3.95) with the descriptive equivalent of extensive and is primarily oftentimes manifested. Furthermore, the finding implies that

teacher cooperation molds the teachers to be satisfied with the field of teaching as this emulsifies bond as well as a support system with one another. This also connotes the embodiment of the cooperative status of the teachers as they uphold dealing with collaborative perspectives and primarily dwell on the advanced features that the new and the upcoming generations.

Table 9. Teacher Teaching Efficacy in terms of Efficacy in Student Engagement

No.	Statement	Mean (\bar{x}) Descriptive Equivalent
1	You can get through to the most difficult students	3.94 Extensive
2	You can assist families in helping their children do well in school	4.05 Extensive
3	You can help your students think critically	4.05 Extensive
4	You can foster student creativity	3.90 Extensive
6	You can foster student creativity	4.01 Extensive
Overall Mean		3.95 Extensive

As a teacher, upholding student engagement in the instructional process is very significant. This will pave the way for the learners to create meaningful learning experiences. As stated by Willms, Friesen, and Milton (2009), understanding student engagement is essential to preventing dropout and ensuring that all students receive a good education. Participation, academic engagement, and intellectual engagement decline starting in middle school and stay low through secondary. They concluded that to activate motivation and improve student achievement, it is crucial to look at the constructs of student engagement.

3.10. *Efficacy in Instructional Strategies*—Table 10 shows the data on teacher teaching efficacy in terms of efficacy in instructional strategies. The data was arranged from the highest to the lowest mean rating obtained: You can use a variety of assessment strategies with a rating of

(4.05) which serves as the highest. You can adjust your lessons to the proper level for individual students with a rating of (4.02); You can implement alternative strategies in your classroom with a mean of (4.00); You can provide an alternative explanation or example when students are confused about having the mean of (3.99); and finally, you can respond to difficult questions from your students with the mean of (3.95) that serves the lowest among them. All items in this indicator yield ratings with a descriptive equivalent of extensive. This has gained an overall mean rating of (4.01) or a descriptive equivalent of extensive, which means that teacher teaching efficacy in instructional strategies is often manifested. This result reveals that teachers demonstrate the importance of workload as a manifestation of job satisfaction. Workload is one of the essential things that school leaders must uphold. Giving teachers a heavy workload

dramatically affects their performance and professional growth. Thus, a school leader must emphasize providing teachers with workloads equally.

Table 10. Teacher Teaching Efficacy in terms of Efficacy in Instructional Strategies

No.	Statement	Mean (\bar{x})	Descriptive Equivalent
1	You can provide an alternative explanation or example when students are confused	3.99	Extensive
2	You can use a variety of assessment strategies	4.05	Extensive
4	You can implement alternative strategies in your classroom	4.00	Extensive
5	You can respond to difficult questions from your students	3.95	Extensive
6	You can adjust your lessons to the proper level for individual students	4.02	Extensive
Overall Mean		4.01	Extensive

The finding conforms to the statement that every stage of a teacher’s career is supported by instructional strategies. Teachers should know how to modify instructional strategies in response to various learning objectives, needs, and school environments. The instructional strategies are a bank of trustworthy instructional techniques that new teachers can confidently use. This resource can help experienced teachers better understand the instructional strategies they already employ and offer fresh ideas for implementing them in the classroom. This resource will be helpful for teachers who are already very familiar with instructional strategies as they work to master these important techniques (State of Vicotria, 2017). Issac (2010) explains that a teacher’s teaching tactics are the behaviors he exhibits in class, such as developing teaching strategies, providing appropriate stimulus for prompt responses, drilling learned responses, increasing responses through additional activities, and so forth.

3.10.1. *Efficacy in Classroom Management* —Table 11 shows the data collected on

teacher teaching efficacy in terms of efficacy in classroom management. The presentation of the data gathered is arranged logically from the highest to the lowest or, in other words, in a logical manner obtained, namely: You can establish routines to keep activities running smoothly, which garnered the mean rating of (4.01); You can establish a classroom management system with each group of students which garnered the mean rating of (4.00); You can get children to follow classroom rules with the mean of (3.90); You can respond to defiant students with the rating of (3.89); You can you do to calm a student who is disruptive or noisy which gained the mean of (3.88) as the lowest. All of the five items on these indicators conceded extensive as their descriptive equivalents. Likewise, this has gained an overall mean of (3.95) with a descriptive equivalent of extensive that primarily indicates that the teacher respondents underpin teacher teaching efficacy in classroom management. Classroom management is one of the most essential things teachers must build on during the first sessions of the class. This

primarily talks about how a teacher will eventually set rules that will help them manage the classroom, especially when there are disruptive behaviors in the instructional processes. For the teachers to be effective in the teaching and learning, they must know and apply how to manage students/learners properly or, in general, the classroom.

Table 11. Teacher Teaching Efficacy in terms of Efficacy in Classroom Management

No.	Statement	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	You can establish a classroom management system with each group of students	4.00	Extensive
2	You can you do to calm a student who is disruptive or noisy	3.88	Extensive
3	You can get children to follow classroom rules	3.90	Extensive
4	You can respond to defiant students	3.89	Extensive
5	You can establish routines to keep activities running smoothly	4.01	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.95	Extensive

This is anchored on the statement that building strong teacher-student relationships is crucial to fostering a positive learning environment in the classroom. School discipline issues can be resolved individually (between the teacher and the student) or collectively (during class meetings). Students are gradually released from teacher supervision by taking on more responsibility as mutual trust between them grows. This is how educators and students work together to maximize their individual and group experiences as co-participants in the teaching-learning

process (Vidhya, 2022).

3.11. *Summary of Teacher Teaching Efficacy*—Table 12 presents the summary of the Teacher teaching efficacy that contains three indicators arranged randomly and shows that the overall mean is (3.96) having the descriptive equivalent of high. The three indicators are presented with their corresponding mean rating, namely: Efficacy in Instructional Strategies (3.99), Efficacy in Classroom Management (3.95), and Efficacy in Student Engagement (3.94).

Table 12. Summary of teaching proficiency of teachers

Indicators	Mean (\bar{x})	Descriptive Equivalent
Efficacy in Student Engagement	3.94	Extensive
Efficacy in Instructional Strategies	3.99	Extensive
Efficacy in Classroom Management	3.95	Extensive
Overall mean	3.96	Extensive

The finding is similar to the results in the study of Dağlı and Kalkan (2021). The Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale was used to collect research data. Descriptive statistics, regression analysis, and path analysis were used to analyze the data. The study’s findings show that according to teachers’ perceptions, school principals’ empowering leadership behaviors are high. Similarly, it was found that teachers’ self-efficacy perceptions and job satisfaction were also at a high level. The results was similar to the study of Amundsen and Martinsen, (2015); Farmanesh and Zargar,(2021) and ; Jia et al., (2022), They concluded that empowering leadership is regarded as a positive and ethical style that disregards the traditional flow of power by emphasizing empowerment and support, which leads to desirable outcomes for staff and the school organization. This is because such leaders can empower their followers from sociocultural (practices, interventions, and tactics for empowerment) and psychological aspects [self-determination, meaning, competence, and influence (Amundsen and Martinsen, 2015)]. Therefore, these leaders are a good fit for academic setting management. Within the context of this

study, it is important to note that empowering leaders can boost trust (Farmanesh and Zargar, 2021) among their staff due to their behavior, and motivational approach that encourages positive exchange and interactions.

3.12. *Relationship between Empowering Behaviors of School Heads And Teacher job Satisfaction and Teaching Efficacy*—Shown in Table 13 are the data on significant relationship between the empowering behaviors of school heads to the job satisfaction of the teachers and on the teaching efficiency of the teachers with the use of Pearson Product –Moment Correlation Coefficient or Pearson r, the results for the computed R-value for the empowering behaviors of school heads and the job satisfaction and teaching efficacy of the teachers is 0.81 which denotes strong relationship with p-value of 0.00 which is lesser than alpha value of 0.05. level of significance. Hence, this finding leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Therefore, technology literacy was observed to have a degree of connection to the teaching proficiency of the teachers. This implies that teachers’ teaching proficiency is significantly related to work technology literacy.

Table 13. The Empowering Behaviors Of School Heads As Predictor Of Teacher Job Satisfaction And Teaching Efficacy

Variables	r-value	Degree of Correlation	P value	Interpretation	Decision
Empowering Behaviors of School Heads (x) Teacher Job Satisfaction (y) Teaching Efficacy (z)	0.81	High	0.00	Significant	Reject

Note: Significance when $P < 0.05$

It provides information that the posed null hypothesis stating that there is no significant

relationship between the empowering behaviors of school heads and teacher job satisfaction

must be rejected for the results provided empirical evidence of significant results. Taking these results, it therefore concludes that empowering behaviors of school heads and teacher job satisfaction. This finding can be inferred statistically that empowering behaviors of school heads is a great factor in promoting extensive job satisfaction of teachers, and by that, they will perform well in their work assignments as they are rated extensively. This finding is similar to the study of Dağlı, and Kalkan, (2021). his study examines the relationship between empowering leadership behaviors of school principals and teachers' self-efficacy perceptions and job satisfaction levels. 260 teachers working in the Antakya district of Hatay province and selected by the stratified sampling method participated in the study. The Empowering Leadership Questionnaire, Teacher Self-Efficacy Belief Scale, and Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale were used

to collect research data. Descriptive statistics, regression analysis, and path analysis were used to analyze the data. The study's findings show that according to teachers' perceptions, school principals' empowering leadership behaviors are high. Similarly, it was found that teachers' self-efficacy perceptions and job satisfaction were also extensive. They added that teaching empowering leadership behavior, self-efficacy, and job satisfaction. Empowering leadership behavior and self-efficacy are significant predictors of job satisfaction. Self-efficacy has a partial mediating effect on the relationship between empowering leadership behavior and job satisfaction. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that the empowering leadership behaviors of school principals, who play an important role in teachers' job satisfaction, have an effect on teachers' self-efficacy.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter discusses the study's main objectives and the statistical analysis results. It also presents the conclusions and recommendations based on the findings gathered in the study.

This study aimed to evaluate the role of the empowering behaviors of the school heads in job satisfaction and teaching efficiency. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions: what is the extent of the empowering behavior of the school heads in terms of giving acknowledgment and recognition, fostering Collaborative Relationships, and providing role-modeling? What is the importance of teachers' job satisfaction regarding teacher cooperation, workload, and leadership support? What is the extent of teachers' teaching efficacy in student engagement, efficacy in Instructional Strategies, and efficacy in classroom management? Is there any significant relationship between the empowering behaviors of the school heads and the job satisfaction of teachers, the empowering behavior of the school heads, and the teaching profi-

ciency of teachers? Which of the domains of the empowering behavior of the school heads significantly influence job satisfaction and teacher teaching proficiency? The findings revealed that the empowering behaviors of school leaders in terms of giving acknowledgment and recognition were extensive and were interpreted as oftentimes manifested. This only highlights the significance of providing recognition to the teachers, which would affect their performance, particularly in teaching pedagogy. It is indeed true that teachers sometimes need motivation, and one of the said motivations is to give them recognition as a reward for all their hard work. School leaders must emphasize recognizing educators working extremely hard to engage and enrich students' lives since they could receive recognition for their hard work and dedication

as educators as it fosters ongoing engagement and validation. Next, it was revealed that empowering behaviors of school leaders in terms of fostering collaborative gained that overall mean contains the descriptive equivalent of extensive and with 4.00 as its value, which connotes that the empowering behaviors of school leaders in terms of fostering collaborative relationships were extensive or interpreted as often manifested. In other words, the data suggests that the teachers are sufficient in their teaching and engage in their learning process through collaborative relationships, as they were rated extensively in this indicator. Collaborative relationships among teachers must also be on the list of school leaders to be portrayed in every school. Strong teamwork and collaborative cultures emerge over time and necessitate dedication to the procedure. Genuine cooperation is complex despite the benefits being obvious. Deep teacher learning that results in measurable student achievement can be achieved by remaining patient in the present and anticipating the outcome. The indicator empowering behaviors of school leaders in terms of providing role-modeling revealed the data that the empowering behaviors of school leaders in terms of providing role-modeling are extensive or interpreted as oftentimes manifested. This means that this indicator, with an overall mean of (3.99) gained the descriptive equivalent of extensive. The followers' attention would be on every move and word made by the leader. His words and deeds gave rise to expectations of what was expected of them. For this reason, a leader should be the first person to follow the rules that an organization established, which are expected to be upheld over time. If done consistently, it significantly impacted the subordinates' motivation. According to this viewpoint, numerous empirical studies supported its integrity. A leader's behavior as a role model effectively shapes organizational citizenship in the subordinates. One of the successful school characteristics was a

leader who served as a role model. The principal played a similar role in structuring the institution's educational system. While in teacher job satisfaction regarding teacher cooperation, the overall mean rating for this indicator was (3.99), which gained the descriptive equivalent of extensive and was primarily interested as often manifested. Regarding leadership support, the overall mean rating for the teacher job satisfaction in terms of teacher cooperation was (3.99) with the descriptive equivalent of extensive and is primarily interpreted as oftentimes manifested. For the last indicator under teacher job satisfaction, teacher workload has gained an overall mean rating of (3.95) or a descriptive equivalent of extensive, which means that job satisfaction in terms of teacher workload was frequently manifested. This only denotes that teachers' job satisfaction increased when they demonstrated high levels of cooperation and collaboration, especially new teachers who are most at risk for leaving the profession. Additionally, when new and experienced teachers collaborated, both groups benefited because the new teachers learned more about their roles, and the experienced teachers acquired fresh approaches to teaching and classroom management. Meanwhile, teacher workload also conforms to teacher job satisfaction. Teacher workload was not an easy thing. Knowing that teachers have a lot of things to work out, such as their personal, family, school, and community factors, sometimes this workload greatly affects how teachers perceive the nature of their work and could eventually reflect how teachers are satisfied with their jobs. For the teacher teaching efficacy in terms of efficacy in student engagement, the overall mean rating for the teacher teaching efficacy in terms of efficacy in student engagement was (3.95) with the descriptive equivalent of extensive and is primarily oftentimes manifested. Next, the data on teacher teaching efficacy in terms of efficacy in instructional strategies revealed an overall mean rating of (4.01) or a descriptive equivalent of extensive,

which means that teacher teaching efficacy in terms of efficacy in instructional strategies was oftentimes manifested. Lastly, teacher teaching efficacy in terms of efficacy in classroom management has gained an overall mean of (3.95) with a descriptive equivalent of extensive that primarily indicates that the teacher respondents underpin that teacher teaching efficacy in terms of efficacy in classroom management. It is indeed one part of being a teachers to provide a quality teaching and learning process where the students are handed with engaging activities wherein students are given the chance to be learn while having fun. Student engagement is one of the things that teachers must build as a platform in the instructional process. One of the best things that the teachers should take in mind is to give the students instructional strategies that supports and awaken the interest of student while learning. On the other hand, classroom management is also a factor that teachers can be raised as efficient inside the classroom. Teachers should know how to facilitate and manage the students, particularly in the teaching and learning process. Similarly, the teacher respondents agreed that the empowering behaviors of school leaders predict a strong bond between teacher job satisfaction and teaching efficacy.

4.1. Conclusions—Based on the overall findings of this research, the following conclusions are drawn: The school heads' empowering behavior in terms of acknowledging and recognizing, fostering Collaborative Relationships, and providing role-modeling was extensive. Teachers' level of teaching proficiency in terms of social, cognitive, and teaching presence. Teachers' job satisfaction regarding teacher cooperation, teacher workload, and leadership support is rated as extensive and interpreted as extensive. The teachers' teaching efficacy in student engagement, Instructional Strategies, and classroom management was rated as extensive. There was a significant relation-

ship between the empowering behaviors of the school heads to the job satisfaction of teachers, and the teaching proficiency of teachers. The empowering behaviors of the school heads suggest that it highlights a strong connection between the job satisfaction of teachers and the teaching proficiency of teachers. Hence, it implies that empowering behaviors of the school heads were significantly connected to the job satisfaction of teachers and the teaching proficiency of teachers.

4.2. Recommendations—In the light of the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are offered for consideration: The School heads and Administrators. The data and information collected on this study would serve as a platform for the school heads and administrators to create dynamic schemes in his or her supervision of school activities for the betterment of the school as well as of the teachers by means of helping them grow particularly on their empowering behavior of the school heads significantly influence the Job Satisfaction and teaching proficiency teachers. They could also become the motivational driving force to keep the burning passion of the teachers in serving the young minds of this generation. They may use this finding to improve their desire to help their respective teachers to improve and engage in school activities. The Teachers. This study would also be significant for the empowering behavior of the school heads significantly influence the Job Satisfaction and teaching proficiency teachers as well as improve their teaching competencies and proceed with the teaching and learning process effectively as they serve as the wheel of the education and the facilitator of learning. They may use this finding to help other teachers to improve their performance to increase their job satisfaction. Lastly, this study would serve as a reference for future researchers as they conduct similar or comparative studies.

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